

A MODERN APPROACH TO THE TREATMENT OF RARE BREAST CANCER

Djumaniyazova G.M

TTA Urganch branch

Introduction: Breast cancer (BC) occupies a leading position in terms of the prevalence of cancer in women worldwide. The annual morbidity and mortality caused by this disease emphasize the urgency of continuing to study its features and search for new approaches to treatment and prevention. In addition to the generally recognized invasive ductal breast cancers, which account for the majority of cases, there is a spectrum of rare histological subtypes, each of which is characterized by individual clinical and pathological features and response to therapeutic interventions.

Purpose to work: of the study is to study the features of the clinical course, characteristics and response to the treatment of rare histological forms of breast cancer.

Material and methods: The study included 102 patients with rare forms of breast cancer and a control group of 54 patients with invasive ductal cancer. An analysis of histological subtypes was carried out, as well as an assessment of clinical and pathological parameters. Statistical methods were used to compare survival and other key metrics between groups.

Research results: The study revealed statistically significant differences in age, histological degree, tumor size, lymph node morbidity and the frequency of stage IV de novo between patients with rare histological forms of breast cancer and standard invasive ductal cancer. In addition, differences were found in the response to therapy in different subtypes of these rare forms.

Conclusions: Rare histological forms of breast cancer demonstrate unique clinical and pathological features and behavior of the disease, which can influence the treatment strategy and prognosis. The results highlight the importance of an individualized approach to the diagnosis and treatment of such patients, as well as the need for in-depth stratification to improve therapeutic outcomes and quality of life.